

On the Issue of Nanoscale KH_2PO_4 and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ Crystals Grown in Porous SiO_2 Matrix: Raman Spectroscopy, X-Ray Diffraction and *Ab Initio* Lattice Dynamics Analysis

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Combining dielectric crystals with mesoporous solids allows a versatile design of functional nanomaterials, where the porous host provides a mechanical rigid scaffold structure and the molecular filling adds the functionalization. Here, we report a study of the complex lattice dynamics of a $\text{SiO}_2:\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4$ nanocomposite consisting of a monolithic, mesoporous silica glass host with KH_2PO_4 nanocrystals embedded in its tubular channels ~ 12 nm across. A micro-Raman investigation performed in the spectral range of $70\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reveals the complex lattice dynamics of the confined crystals. Their Raman spectrum resembles the one taken from bulk KH_2PO_4 crystals and thus, along with X-ray diffraction experiments, corroborates the successful solution-based synthesis of KH_2PO_4 nanocrystals with a structure analogous to the bulk material. We succeeded in observing not only the high-frequency internal modes ($\sim 900\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), typical of internal vibrations of the PO_4 tetrahedra, but, more importantly, also the lowest frequency modes typical of bulk KH_2PO_4 crystals. The experimental Raman spectrum was interpreted with a group theory analysis and first-principle lattice dynamics calculations.

We have studied the lattice dynamics of nanoscale $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ crystals embedded in monolithic, mesoporous silica glass host, SiO_2 , with non-regular system of $10\text{-}12$ nm diameter pores. To interpret the Raman scattering of $\text{SiO}_2:\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ nanocomposite the polarized Raman spectra of bulk $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ single crystal were investigated. Since the cubic symmetry (sp.gr. Pa-3, No.20) is inherent for $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, the special geometry of Raman scattering experiment was utilized to separate the phonon modes of A_g and E_g species. Combining group-theory analysis and *ab initio* lattice dynamics calculation we performed the detailed interpretation of all Raman lines of bulk single crystal. The Raman scattering of $\text{SiO}_2:\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ nanocomposite reveals an existence of comparatively large, $\sim 10\text{-}20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, single crystalline regions of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ which are of near three orders of magnitude larger than the average spacing of SiO_2 pores. A thorough analysis of Raman lines shape has showed that the peak positions and normalized peak intensities of Raman spectra of the bulk $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ single crystal and its nanoscale counterpart embedded in SiO_2 host are very similar. The full widths at half maximum (FWHM) of Raman lines below $\sim 150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of nanosized $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ are mainly larger than those of monolithic bulk single crystal. Such increase of FWHM is the result of spatial confinement effect relevant for nanoconfined crystals embedded in porous SiO_2 matrix.

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